

USE OF DIDACTIC GAMES IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE LESSONS

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Abstract: This article talks about the theoretical and practical importance of using didactic games in English classes of general secondary schools. Also, the theoretical foundations of didactic games are explained.

Key words: English language, didactic games, word game, theory, methodology, educational system.

Education has always been very important in human activity. This was the case even when learning was random, intuitive, and consisted mainly of random information and imitation; later, when education became a regular and planned process according to the purpose, it was the same when the school appeared. However, theoretical analysis and study of education was not carried out for a long time, so it did not have its own theory. Only the 17th century brought significant changes in this field: it was at that time that education received a special name and the first scientifically based system of didactic activity in history was founded.

Didactics (the theory of education: the Greek "didaktikos" means "teacher, and "didasko" means "learner") theoretical aspects of education (the essence, principles, laws of the educational process, the teacher and a science that studies the content of student activity, educational goals, form, methods, tools, results, ways to improve the educational process, etc. problems).

This word was introduced in Germany in 1613 by the German pedagogue Wolfgang Rathke (1571-1635). The great Czech pedagogue Jan Amos Comenius (1592-1670) mentions this concept in a similar way in his famous work "The Great Didactic". But Comenius emphasizes that "didactics" is not only education, but also upbringing. In this work, the scientist talks about the important issues of the theory of education: the content of education, the principles of demonstration and sequence of education, and the class-lesson system.

The subject, functions and task of didactics. The science of pedagogy studies the process of education and upbringing based on their integrity and unity. To clearly explain the essence of each of the two activities, they distinguish didactics (theory of education) and the theory of education. In the present period, didactics is understood as a field of pedagogy that scientifically substantiates the content, methods and organizational forms of teaching.

The subject of general didactics is the interdependence and connection between teaching (teacher's activity) and learning (student's learning activity).

The tasks of didactics are as follows:

- description and explanation of educational processes and conditions for their implementation;
- more perfect organization of the educational process, that is, development of educational systems and technologies;
- to identify, analyze and describe the general laws specific to the educational process.

Didactics is a theoretical and at the same time normative-practical science. The scientific-theoretical task of didactics is to study the existing processes of education, the connections between its various aspects, to reveal their essence, to determine the development trends and the future. The acquired theoretical knowledge allows to direct the educational practice, to improve education in accordance with the social requirements imposed by the society. Didactics performs a practical-normative and organizational-technological task on the basis of understanding the content of education, determining the norms of the application of educational principles and educational methods and tools.

The essence and task of the educational process. Teaching and imparting knowledge play a major role in the education of a person, in the development and formation of a person's personality. Education appeared in the first stages of its development in human society. Children imitate adults, repeat their actions, the processes of making and using work tools, take examples from their behavior, learn colloquial terms and their meaning. Imitating adults and growing up, children learn the laws of nature, deepen and improve their knowledge.

The educational process is two-way, in which there are two persons - a teacher and a student. They have a certain relationship that is unique to a certain process. they perform completely opposite roles - the roles of teaching and reading. Teaching means imparting knowledge to students, forming skills and competencies in them, training creative and logical thinking capable of discovering new truths.

Alifbo o`yini

Bu o`yin ingliz tilini endi o`rganayotganlar uchun hisoblanib 7-8 yoshli bolalar uchun. O`yida oldidan tayorlangan harflar yozilgan ko`rgazmali qurol bo`ladi. Buo`yin orqali bolalarni alifbo harflarini qay darajada yod olganliklari va ularning birinchi harfi bilan qanday so`z boshlanishini esga oladilar.

<u>Questions:</u>	<u>Answers:</u>
Find letter a	a is for apple
Find letter b	b is for banana
Find letter c	c is for cat
Find letter d	d is for dog
Find letter e	e is for elephant
Find letter f	f is for fish
Find letter g	g is for gorilla
Find letter h	h is for house
Find letter i	i is for ice cream
Find letter j	j is for jet
Find letter k	k is for koala
Find letter l	l is for lion
Find letter m	m is for mouse
Find letter n	n is for nest
Find letter o	o is for octopus
Find letter p	p is for pig
Find letter q	q is for queen
Find letter r	r is for rabbit
Find letter s	s is for snake

Find letter t	t is for teddy
Find letter u	u is for umbrella
Find letter v	v is for vegetables
Find letter w	w is for whale
Find letter x	x is for xylophone
Find letter y	y is for yo-yo
Find letter z	z is for zebra

The alphabet game.

Purpose: to repeat the letters of the alphabet.

Level of language change: beginner and intermediate.

Necessary tools for the game: 26 letters of the alphabet written in printed letters on separate cardboards.

Conducting the game: show the students mixed letters of the alphabet, it is appropriate to remove "q, x and z", we tell the students to pay attention to the selected special categories: flowers, supermarket products, furniture, vegetables, clothes, etc. Their choice depends on the criteria of the categories they are studying and their own vocabulary. The game starts when the student shows the letter. The student who said the first in the selected category will receive a letter card. At the end of the game, the student who gets the most cards is considered the winner. If several students say the same word at the same time, the card is put back to be used again later. This game can be played in groups, the group with the most cards is the game. the winner will be announced at the end.

Bananas. Purpose and condition: to practice the Wh question (special question) form. One player is chosen to be the "dog" or comes out at will. The rest of the playing students should ask different questions about the personality of "dog" in the form of Wh-question. The answerer must answer "Bananas" to all questions. The goal of the game is to make the "dog" laugh. Whose question caused the answerer to laugh, that student becomes the "dog" and the game continues.

The questions should be such that their answer should be funny. In this thought

It is forbidden to ask "yes" or "no" questions. Only "Wh-question" must be a special interrogative sentence. Because this game is popular and fun, students may want to play it again and again. Therefore, "Bananas" can be replaced by other words. In this case, the game will be interesting even if you change the name of the object or animal.

Chain game.

Purpose: To test and improve memory.

The game is played in groups and at the beginning one subject should be limited from the circle. For example, "Animals" in which the first student says a word and says for example 'cow', the other student repeats the first student's word "cow" and says his new word i.e. It continues by saying the word "pig". The player who stops playing will leave the game. If there are 10 or more people in the group, the number of words will increase and it will be interesting. ladi You can test your memory through the game, find out how much it is and increase it.

For example:

Guess my job.

Purpose: to strengthen various professions and related words.

Necessary tools: a set of cards with the names of professions.

Cards with the names of various professions are put in an envelope. A volunteer student is called from the group and one card is chosen. Students sitting alternately ask only general questions (Yes/No questions) to find the hidden occupation on the card. The student holding the card can only answer "Yes" or "No". The student who found the name of the profession first takes the place of the student standing in the middle and then takes the card. The game continues like this.

Actor	lawyer	architect	Model
Fortune-teller	doctor	sculptor	pilot
Nurse	driver	Cook	gardener
Teacher	plumber	carpenter	secretary
Shop assistant	vet	policeman	astronomer
Barber	designer	accountant	singer

In conclusion, we can make these games easier or harder depending on the level or age of the children. The purpose of these interactive games is different. Through these games, we can concentrate, increase vocabulary, quickness, intelligence, and most importantly, learn and remember the lesson in an interesting way.

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